

Energy Efficiency Performance-Tracking Platform for Benchmarking Savings and Investments in Buildings

EN-TRACK & DEEP mapping to BEDES

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Authors:	CIMNE - Stoyan Danov, Eloi Gabaldon, Francesc Contreras

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Peer reviewed by:

Partner	Reviewer
EnEffectConsult	Stanislav Andreev
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Abbreviations and Acronyms

Acronym	Description
BEDES	Building Energy Data Exchange Specification
DEEP	De-risking Energy Efficiency Platform
EEFIG	Energy Efficiency Financial Institutions Group
EEM	Energy Efficiency Measure
LBL	Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory
US	United States

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1 Executive summary

The current document provides a summary of the work for mapping the EN-TRACK data model to the BEDES specification of common terms and to the DEEP database fields. The work has been done within the task of standardisation of data and interoperability assuring of EN-TRACK.

The document describes the approach and procedures followed in the process of mapping and provides some examples of this in the text. The initial mapping files have been uploaded in the open repository Zenodo and links to them have been provided in the document.

The mapping to BEDES has required considerable effort both in terms of gaining sufficient familiarisation with the BEDES terminology and its mapping procedures, and also in consultation and collaboration with the BEDES developing team. The work has revealed some limitations for the full mapping of the EN-TRACK data model to BEDES. These relate to a lack of capability of BEDES to describe the structure of data, and insufficient expressive power to describe timeseries data and taxonomies, among others. Consequently, the pragmatic solution has been to develop a partial mapping document and to reconsider the initial idea of mapping the full EN-TRACK model. This reconsideration, in collaboration with the BEDES team, has led to the idea of a more targeted mapping, focusing particularly on the fields necessary for data exchange and omitting the mapping of the internal fields. Despite the limited scope, the initial mapping was considered very beneficial for facilitating future data exchange between BEDES compliant applications and European tools. The work will continue with the objective to achieve official BEDES compliance.

The mapping to DEEP has been successfully completed in first version and has been achieved without substantial difficulties due to the early alignment during the design of the EN-TRACK data model. This first version provides a sufficiently solid base for implementation of data exchange between both platforms. The mapping will be reviewed and updated towards the end of the EN-TRACK project in the light of any possible changes that might be made in the EN-TRACK model during the implementation and testing, as any changes that might be made in DEEP during the same period.

To summarise the outcomes of the work:

- The vast majority, 175 of the 210 data fields in DEEP were successfully mapped to EN-TRACK, covering all essential fields. This very satisfying result is a consequence of the solid preparatory work in the design phase of EN-TRACK towards ensuring compatibility between the two applications.
- The resultant mapping document enables the mapping of EN-TRACK to BEDES to also be re-used for DEEP, by associating both mapping files through the EN-TRACK attributes. This will be helpful for achieving compliance of DEEP with BEDES, if this is considered in the future.
- As a result of the work done, and in collaboration with the BEDES developing team it has been decided that on-going work will focus on specific use cases for BEDES-enabled data exchange, with particular applications, when the definitive model is completed and tested.

2 Background

The overall aim of the EN-TRACK project is to enable massive gathering of data to support decision making in building energy efficiency actuations, contributing to mainstreaming of the energy efficiency financing through de-risking of the investments on the base of provision of reliable empirical evidence of their effect. EN-TRACK also aims to enable exchange of data with other existing applications on the European market, especially with the DEEP [1] and eQuad platforms, as well as to align its terminology to the BEDES [2] specification of common terms, referenced to a large number of applications in the U.S.

The basic premise of EN-TRACK is that most of the needed data already exists, but they are inaccessible and badly organised, which represents a big challenge. Data are being stored in decentralised databases and tools, in different formats, and with ambiguous definitions, which is hindering their use for coherent analysis and conclusions. EN-TRACK approaches the solution to this problem by developing of a comprehensive data model (the EN-TRACK data model) that serves as a common reference for alignment of data from different sources. The exchange of information requires previous association of the external data elements with those of EN-TRACK to ensure unambiguously shared meaning and interpretation.

3 Introduction

The current document contributes to the Task 1.5 Standardisation of data and assuring interoperability of EN-TRACK, and reports on the translation of the EN-TRACK data model into the BEDES terminology, as well as on the alignment of the DEEP data fields to those of EN-TRACK. The term “mapping” is used in this context for the association of the elements of one dataset with those of other.

BEDES is a dictionary of common terms that has been developed by the US Department of Energy to improve the interoperability of its software tools and data collection efforts. It is currently used as a reference for more than 50 databases and applications in the US, including the comprehensive Building Performance Database with more than 1 million of commercial and residential building entries. The mapping to BEDES allows EN-TRACK to become a part of this ecosystem of interoperable tools.

DEEP, developed by the Energy Efficiency Financial Institutions Group (EEFIG), is the largest pan-European open-source database containing detailed technical and financial performance data of industrial and buildings related energy efficiency projects. EN-TRACK is strongly committed to contribute data to DEEP, and the mapping to DEEP is a necessary step to enable automated exchange between both databases. At the same time, the mapping will help for the future alignment (through EN-TRACK) of DEEP to BEDES, opening new possible data sources for DEEP.

The next sections of the document describe the procedures for mapping of the EN-TRACK data model to BEDES and to DEEP and discuss the current results and the problems found. The mappings themselves, which are done in Excel files, are on the open data repository Zenodo. Links to these mapping files are provided in the respective sections of this document.

4 Mapping to BEDES

4.1 Procedure

BEDES is designed to support analysis of the measured energy performance of commercial and residential buildings, with fields for building characteristics, efficiency measures and energy use. BEDES does not impose any specific data model, rather it focuses on establishing a common language for describing data that can be used across data sets and implementation tools. The goal for BEDES is to serve as a central “data dictionary” that a range of tools and platforms can either utilize or map to. Depending on the needs of the specific use cases, different BEDES-compliant data models and schemes can be implemented.

The translation of the EN-TRACK data model terminology to BEDES aims to use the latter as middle ground for aligning EN-TRACK with external applications from the BEDES-compliant ecosystem, and also to eliminate the possibility of misinterpretations.

The mapping followed the procedure and the template provided by Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory (LBNL) [3], the fields of which are presented in Table 1. A spreadsheet was prepared to establish a mapping of EN-TRACK’s attributes and enumerations to BEDES terms. The process first required familiarisation with the most recent version of the vocabulary (V2.4) and its atomic terms, followed by an in-depth study of the compliance procedure. The mapping was established by the following steps:

- 1) Create a spreadsheet tab for each class of the EN-TRACK data model containing the fields of the template and filling those corresponding to the EN-TRACK terms (corresponding to rows n° 1-5 in the Table 1)
- 2) Identify the EN-TRACK attributes that can be directly translated to a BEDES atomic term and recording this term in row n°6 (Table 1).
- 3) Produce composite BEDES terms for the remaining attributes by researching the appropriate combination of atomic terms, by researching the appropriate combination of atomic terms, to be listed in order in row n°10.
- 4) Complete the BEDES term information as required by rows n°7 and n°9
- 5) Derive an appropriate unit conversion, if applicable and necessary, and record it in row n°8.

For the mapping of the taxonomies created for the attributes of enumerated datatype, the procedure is repeated from steps 2 to 5.

1	EN-TRACK Class Name	<i>Class1</i>		
2	EN-TRACK Attribute	<i>attributeA</i>	<i>attributeB</i>	...
3	EN-TRACK Attribute Description	<i>Description of attributeA</i>	<i>Description of attributeB</i>	...
4	EN-TRACK Attribute Unit	<i>Measurement unit of attributeA</i>	<i>Measurement unit of attributeA</i>	...
5	EN-TRACK Attribute Data Type	<i>Data type of attributeA</i>	<i>Data type of attributeB</i>	...

6	BEDES Term	<i>termA</i>	<i>termB</i>	...
7	BEDES Term Units	<i>Measurement unit termA</i>	<i>Measurement unit termA</i>	...
8	Unit conversion	<i>Unit conversion between attributeA and termA if applicable</i>	<i>Unit conversion between attributeB and termB if applicable</i>	...
9	BEDES Term Data Type	<i>Datatype of termA</i>	<i>Datatype of termB</i>	...
10	BEDES Atomic Term Mapping	<i>Atomic terms that form termA</i>	<i>Atomic terms that form termA</i>	...

Table 1. Template used to map EN-TRACK to BEDES V2.4.

4.2 Example

A mapping is presented in Table 2 for the attributes of the class Area of the EN-TRACK model. The three attributes in this class provide i) an example of direct mapping to an atomic BEDES term, in the case of *areaValue*, and ii) two examples of composite BEDES term creation, in the case of *areaType* and *areaUnitOfMeasurement*. The table also highlights one of the challenges identified during the mapping effort, which is the bias of BEDES towards the use of imperial units. In fact, the decision made in EN-TRACK at the design stage to allow the collection of data with different measurement units (i.e. the creation of one attribute to store the unit type), is now found to complicate the definition of the unit conversion to BEDES (see row n°8).

1	EN-TRACK Class Name	<i>Area</i>		
2	EN-TRACK Attribute	<i>areaType</i>	<i>areaValue</i>	<i>areaUnitOfMeasurement</i>
3	EN-TRACK Attribute Description	<i>Type of the measured area</i>	<i>Numerical value of the area</i>	<i>Unit of measurement of the area value</i>
4	EN-TRACK Attribute Unit	/	/	<i>m2</i>
5	EN-TRACK Attribute Data Type	<i>Enum</i>	<i>Float</i>	<i>Enum</i>
6	BEDES Term	<i>Area Description</i>	<i>Area</i>	<i>Area Unit of Measure</i>
7	BEDES Term Units	/	/	<i>ft2</i>

8	Unit conversion		<i>Conversion should be done according the value of areaUnitOfMeasurement</i>	
9	BEDES Term Data Type	<i>Constrained list</i>	<i>Decimal</i>	<i>Constrained list</i>
10	BEDES Atomic Term Mapping	<i>Premises Level = Area, Description = [value]</i>	<i>Area = [value]</i>	<i>Premises Level = Area, Unit of Measure = [value]</i>

Table 2. Mapping to BEDES of the attributes belonging to the class Area of EN-TRACK, transposed here for better visualisation.

An example of taxonomy mapping is provided in Table 3. The example includes the provisional mappings of the taxonomies created for the two attributes of enumerated datatype in the class Area and illustrates the creation of BEDES composite terms. The two cells coloured in light blue present two cases that required the introduction of customised qualifiers because one or more terms that are necessary to fully express the meaning of an EN-TRACK attribute do not exist in BEDES V2.4.

EN-TRACK Attribute	EN-TRACK Enum Term	BEDES Constrained List Option	BEDES Atomic Term Mapping
areaType	GrossFloorArea	Gross Floor Area	Floor Area Qualifier = Gross, Opaque Surface = Floor, Area = [value]
	GrossFloorAreaAboveGround	Gross Above Grade Floor Area	Floor Area Qualifier = Gross, Location = Above Grade Opaque Surface = Floor, Area = [value]
	GrossFloorAreaUnderGround	Gross Below Grade Floor Area	Floor Area Qualifier = Gross, Location = Below Grade Opaque Surface = Floor, Area = [value]
	NetFloorArea	Net Floor Area	Floor Area Qualifier = Net, Opaque Surface = Floor, Area = [value]

	CooledFloorArea	Cooled Floor Area	Conditioning Status = Cooled, Opaque Surface = Floor, Area = [value]
	HeatedFloorArea	Heated Floor Area	Conditioning Status = Heated, Opaque Surface = Floor, Area = [value]
	CadastralParcelArea	Cadastral Parcel Floor Area	Floor Area Qualifier = Custom, Custom Floor Area Qualifier = "Cadastral Parcel" Opaque Surface = Floor, Area = [value]
areaUnitOf	ft2	ft2	Unit of Measure = ft2
	m2	m2	Unit of Measure = m2
	Other	Other	Unit of Measure = Custom, Custom Unit Of Measure = "Other"

Table 3. Mapping to BEDES of the taxonomies defined for the attributes of enumerated data type belonging to the class Area of EN-TRACK.

4.3 Output and findings

At the current stage of the project (month 18) a preliminary mapping (v1) has been completed as a first step towards establishment of EN-TRACK compliance with the BEDES dictionary. The mapping file has been published in the open repository Zenodo and can be accessed and downloaded in the following link:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6656423>

The mapping has been consulted with the BEDES implementation team from LBNL, and technical indications were received. The BEDES team propose pausing the work on mapping until the EN-TRACK model is fully concluded and its functionality is tested in the pilots. Their logic is that the viability of compliance has been successfully validated at this initial stage and the considerable extra effort required to achieve full BEDES compliance is not sufficiently justified yet because the possible modifications in the ongoing development of the EN-TRACK platform mean that the resulting mapping would only be provisional. The initial alignment of EN-TRACK is considered very beneficial for facilitating future data exchange between BEDES compliant applications and European tools. Moreover, some promising future possibilities emerged from the conversations with the BEDES implementation team, among which are the implementation of an EEM-specific terminology, which could entirely solve the problem of translation of the EEM enumeration, and the opportunity of publicly including EN-TRACK mapping on the BEDES platform webpage once compliance is reached. This would promote EN-TRACK

enormously and would also help to exchange data with a variety of third-party applications.

Some conclusions were derived from the mapping to BEDES. The work highlighted some of the shortcomings in the expressive power of the BEDES dictionary when applied to the data model developed in EN-TRACK. The challenges identified from the mapping exercise can be summarised as follows:

- Bias towards American standards, which complicates or precludes establishing mappings and measurement unit conversion rules.
- Lack of EEM-specific terminology, which results in the impossibility of properly mapping the EEMs taxonomy
- Lack of terminology to describe time-series measurement, a feature of extreme importance in EN-TRACK's model.
- Necessity of introducing customised qualifiers to perform specific translations, which partly defeats the effort of standardisation since they introduce new terms that are not unambiguously defined in the dictionary, as shown in the provided examples
- Repetitions of terms in different contexts and lack of schema structure, resulting in non-univocal mappings to composite BEDES terms which would complicate future harmonisation effort to other compliant applications.

5 Mapping to DEEP

5.1 Introduction and procedure

DEEP is an open-source database for energy efficiency investments performance monitoring and benchmarking. It aims to increase the energy efficiency financing through improved understanding of the real risks and benefits of energy efficiency investments based on market evidence and investment track records.

The mapping to DEEP was based on the last available description of the DEEP database fields (EEFIG Database Input Template (Macro) V1_8_160221.xlsm). The DEEP database contains a total of 210 data fields, however only 20 of them are essential. During the process of mapping, all of the data fields were analysed, and particular attention was paid to ensuring the mapping of the essential fields. The analysis revealed that some of the DEEP fields were not relevant to EN-TRACK (such as those referring to investments in industry) and other lacked a defined counterpart because matchings were expected to be found with the analytics outputs of EN-TRACK, which were yet to be modelled in detail. Overall, 175 of the total of 210 data fields of DEEP were mapped to EN-TRACK, covering all essential fields.

The mapping has been done in an Excel template by aligning the DEEP fields to those of EN-TRACK. The corresponding data fields of the template are shown in Table 4, transposed for convenience from columns to rows, and explained. The first two columns of the table indicate, respectively, the IDs and names of the data fields used in DEEP. The following column indicates which attribute, object relation, or combination of these was found to match the DEEP data fields, whereas column four identifies the class or classes containing these attributes. The final column indicates the eventual annotations necessary to explain the logic to be followed during the implementation of the data exchange procedure to match the data content of the two sources. Fields for which correspondence is not available in EN-TRACK's model are marked with n/a.

1	DEEP Field ID	<i>Unique identifier of the data field in DEEP</i>
2	DEEP Field Name	<i>Description of the DEEP data field</i>
3	EN-TRACK Attribute	<i>Unique EN-TRACK data field name</i>
4	EN-TRACK Class Name	<i>The data group (class) containing the EN-TRACK data field</i>
5	Notes	<i>Annotations to the mapping</i>

Table 4. Template to map DEEP to EN-TRACK.

The analysis of the fields during the mapping showed that for a considerable part of the data fields, direct matching between DEEP and EN-TRACK could be found. This very satisfying result is a consequence of the effort already made in the design phase of EN-TRACK towards ensuring compatibility between the two applications. The remaining fields required a more complex procedure to match the data. In most cases, this was a consequence of the structural choices made to create a model structure in EN-TRACK capable of accommodating a wider range of data than DEEP. As an example, data field number 18 of DEEP, "Which measures are included in the investment", cannot be directly

mapped to one of EN-TRACK's attributes because in EN-TRACK, EEMs are modelled as classes and include more information than just their type. Therefore, importing data from DEEP will necessitate the creation of multiple EnergyEfficiencyMeasure classes connected to the RenovationProject of interest and, for each of them, the value of the energyEfficiencyMeasureType should be set to the one specified in DEEP.

The mapping of the taxonomies for the enumerated data types of EN-TRACK in some cases has been possible with one-to-one matching with the taxonomies (called lists) of DEEP. Nevertheless, the more detailed taxonomies developed in EN-TRACK, structured in different levels, exhibit one-to-many relations from DEEP to EN-TRACK. An example is the EnergyEfficiencyMeasures (EEM) taxonomy of EN-TRACK. For the purpose of exporting data from EN-TRACK to DEEP, each of the mapped detailed EEMs of EN-TRACK should be associated to the more generic EEM in DEEP. For the opposite data exchange from DEEP to EN-TRACK, the DEEP field of the taxonomy should be associated with the highest level of the corresponding multiple EN-TRACK fields.

The resultant mapping document enables the mapping of EN-TRACK to BEDES to also be re-used for DEEP, by associating both mapping files through the EN-TRACK attributes. This will be helpful for achieving compliance of DEEP with BEDES, if this is considered in the future.

5.2 Essential fields mapping

In this section the mapping of the essential fields of DEEP is presented as an example in Table 5. The complete mapping file is accessible in the open repository Zenodo through the following link:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6656451>

DEEP		EN-TRACK		
ID	Name	Attribute(s) / relation(s)	Class(es)	Mapping notes
(1)	Project ID	projectID	RenovationProject	Direct mapping
(2)	Project Title	projectTitle	RenovationProject	Direct mapping
(3)	Country	addressCountry	LocationInfo	Direct mapping
(5)	City/locality	addressCity	LocationInfo	Direct mapping
(12)	Is the investment in a building, in industry, or in infrastructure?	n/a	n/a	EN-TRACK is related only to buildings
(13)	Industry Sector/ Organisation type	n/a	n/a	n/a
(14)	Organisation size	n/a	n/a	n/a
(15)	Building type	buildingUseType	Building	Direct mapping
(16)	Ownership	buildingOwnership	Building	Direct mapping
(17)	Floor area of building (m2)	areaValue; areaUnitOfMeasurement	Area	Mapping to <i>area Value</i> with <i>area Unit Of Measurement = m2</i>

(18)	Which Measures are included in the investment	includesMeasure relation between RenovationProject and EnergyEfficiency Measure classes; energyEfficiencyMeasure Type attribute	EnergyEfficiency Measure	Multiple <i>Energy Efficiency Measures</i> instances need to be connected to the <i>Renovation Project</i> , and for each the energy <i>Efficiency Measure Types</i> should be set accordingly
(29)	Date investment became operational (month/year)	projectOperationalDate	RenovationProject	Direct mapping
(31)	Energy Consumption BEFORE intervention (kWh/y)	measurementValue; measuredProperty; measurementStart; measurementEnd	MeasurementList; Measurement	Mapping to measurement Value with measured Property = Energy Consumption Total and measurement Start and measurement End set to indicate the appropriate reference year
(36)	Predicted Energy Consumption AFTER intervention (kWh/year)	measurementValue; measuredProperty; measurementStart; measurementEnd; measurementType Energy	MeasurementList; Measurement	Mapping to measurement Value with measurement Property = Energy Consumption Total, measurement Type Energy = Predicted, and measurement Start and measurement End set to indicate the appropriate reference year
(38)	Actual Energy Consumption AFTER	measurementValue; measuredProperty;	MeasurementList; Measurement	Mapping to measurement

	intervention (kWh/year)	measurementStart; measurementEnd; measurementType Energy		Value with measurement Property = Energy Consumption Total, measurement Type Energy = Actual, and measurement Start and measurement End set to indicate the appropriate reference year
(51)	Value of EE investment	projectInvestment	RenovationProject	Direct mapping
(55)	Net annual saving (€)	n/a	n/a	n/a
(61)	Value of grant/subsidy (if any) (€)	projectInvestment; projectReceivedGrant Funding; projectGrantsShareOf Costs	RenovationProject	If the value is different than zero, project Received Grant Funding = Yes, and project If the value is different than zero, project Received Grant Funding = Yes, and project If the value is different than zero, project Received Grant Funding = Yes, and project
(67)	Please state all the additional benefits triggered by the project	nonEnergyBenefitType	NonEnergyBenefit	Multiple Non Energy Benefit instances need to be connected to the Renovation Project, and for each of them the Energy Benefit Type should be set accordingly
(68)	Please rate actual financial perfor- mance	n/a	n/a	

	compared with expectation			
(71)	Energy savings total (kWh/y)	energySavingsType; energySavingsValue	EnergySavings	Mapping to energy Savings Value with energy Savings Type = Total Energy

Table 5. DEEP essential fields mapping to EN-TRACK

6 Conclusions

A first version mapping of the EN-TRACK data model to BEDES has been produced. This preliminary mapping involved considerable work in familiarisation with the BEDES terminology and the mapping procedures, and also in the rewarding process involving interaction with the BEDES developing team. It is evident from the work that mapping to BEDES is a difficult task. It is not purely scientific work: it includes considerable scope for interpretation and also presents some challenges/limitations that must be addressed creatively. The main limitation is that BEDES, being a dictionary, is not capable of describing the structure of the data and also presents difficulties in straightforward mapping of timeseries and taxonomies.

As a result of these issues, the initial idea of mapping the whole EN-TRACK data model has been reconsidered. The new idea is, instead of complete mapping, to focus on specific use cases for BEDES-enabled data exchange, with particular applications, when the definitive model is completed and tested. This decision was encouraged by the BEDES developing team. They advised for targeted mapping with clear idea of its use, and against complete mapping at this stage, arguing that the huge work effort that would be required is insufficiently justified because of the risk of the mapping done at such an early stage, becoming obsolete due to the evolving of BEDES itself.

Taking the above into consideration, the future mapping updates will focus particularly on the data fields representing values to be exchanged with external applications and will not target the mapping of the internal fields. The mapping files will be updated on the open repositories, maintaining the objective to achieve official BEDES compliance.

The mapping to DEEP hasn't presented substantial difficulties due to the early alignment during the design of the EN-TRACK data model and has been successfully completed in first version. Currently, it represents a solid basis for implementation of data exchange between both platforms. The mapping will be reviewed and updated towards the end of the project to adapt for the changes in the EN-TRACK model that may occur during the implementation and testing as well as any possible changes in DEEP during the same period of time.

7 References

- [1] De-risking Energy Efficiency Platform (DEEP), <https://deep.eefig.eu>
- [2] Building Energy Data Exchange Specification (BEDES), <https://bedes.lbl.gov>
- [3] BEDES. 2021. BEDES Compliance. [online] Available at: <https://bedes.lbl.gov/bedes-compliance>

